

Application and Use of Research Support Tools for improved academic performance by Post-Graduate Students of Faculty of Social and Management Science of Modibbo Adama University Yola, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explores the application and use of research support tools among post-graduate students at the Faculty of Social and Management Sciences, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Nigeria. The objectives are to; determine the types of research support tools, ascertain the level of application and use of research support tools and to find out the challenges associated with the use of research support tools and three research questions were used to guide the study.

Methodology: The study employed a quantitative research design and used questionnaire as instrument for data collection. The population of the study consists of 215 postgraduate students. The researchers used consensus as the sampling technique, therefore entire population was used. Descriptive statistics were used for data analysis, specifically mean frequency and percentages presented in table.

Findings/Results: The findings of the study revealed that, the postgraduate students are aware and used research support tools having a grand mean of 3.1. The result shows that all application tools are widely used and applied in carrying out research activities. And the study shows that lack of network connectivity and training requirement as pressing challenges.

Implications: The awareness and use of research support tools among postgraduate students highlights the relevance and impacts of these tools in enhancing research activities. However, the identified challenges indicate a need for institutional interventions to improve effectiveness.

Conclusion: The study concludes that postgraduate students actively engage with research support tools but face challenges with their application and use such as poor network connectivity and need for proper training.

Recommendations: The study further recommends that institutions should organize regular training and workshops to deepen student's understanding of research support tools, integrate these tools into academic curricula and put training programs in place to address challenges faced with their use.

Keywords: Research Support Tools, Post-Graduate Students, Academic Performance, and AI and Machine Learning.

Introduction

Conducting research is time-consuming and challenging for finding a solution to a problem. Expertise in research methodology, data collection, and analysis is necessary for any researcher. According to Sallam, (2023), he defined Research Support Tools (RSTs) as to various digital or non-digital resources, services or software applications designed to facilitate and enhance the research process. Research Support Tools are specialized software applications, digital platforms or services that facilitate researcher's workflow, organization and productivity throughout the research lifestyle from literature review to publication and dissemination, Rice et al, (2024). Research is the common parlance that refers to the search for knowledge. It is also any activity which helps to gain fresh insight into something. Research is an endeavor to arrive at answers to intellectual and practical problems through the application of scientific methods to the knowledgeable universe. Research support tools promote the research process of a researcher. These tools will escort the researcher how to search beyond Google, and to catch suitable resources, and to use these resources for their research. Research support tools are digital or physical resources, services, or systems designed to assist researchers throughout the research process from idea development and literature review to data collection, analysis, writing, and dissemination. These tools enhance research efficiency, accuracy, collaboration, and overall quality. "Research support tools refer to the wide array of services and technologies used to support researchers in conducting, managing, and disseminating research. These include reference managers, data analysis software, plagiarism checkers, and institutional support services among others." OECD (2021). Digital Research Infrastructure: Enhancing Research Productivity and Collaboration.

Students use various types of research support tools that aid different stages of the research process. These include reference management tools like Zotero and Mendeley for organizing and citing sources; data analysis software such as SPSS, R, and NVivo for analyzing quantitative and qualitative data; writing and editing tools like Grammarly and LaTeX for improving clarity and formatting; and plagiarism checkers like Turnitin to ensure originality. Additionally, project

management tools like Trello and Notion help students plan and organize their work, while collaboration platforms such as Google Docs and overleaf support teamwork and joint writing efforts. The research tools can minimize the effort /difficulty of the researcher in their research work.

Scientific writing plays a crucial role in the career growth of a researcher and helps gain recognition for them. Research support tools are essential for students as they streamline the research process, enhance accuracy, and promote academic integrity. These tools assist with tasks such as literature management, data analysis, writing, citation, and plagiarism detection, thereby improving the quality and efficiency of academic work. They also help students stay organized, collaborate effectively, and develop critical research and digital skills that are valuable for both academic and professional success. By using these tools, students can conduct more rigorous, ethical, and impactful research.

A postgraduate is a student who has successfully completed an undergraduate degree level course at a college or university and is undertaking further study at a more advanced level. Postgraduate students are experienced in the academic work and research necessary for their subject and spend a great deal of time completing independent study projects. These students engage in advanced study and research within a specific field or discipline, often focusing on developing specialized knowledge, critical thinking, and independent research skills. Postgraduate education may be coursework-based, research-based, or a combination of both, and is aimed at preparing students for professional practice, academic careers, or expert roles in various industries. This means that the little free time that they spend socializing and relaxing outside of their courses is important as many postgraduate students are very focused on their future careers. Therefore, Postgraduate students need to utilize these research tools in order to enhance their academic pursuit. Such tools may include ChatGPT. Library Management Software, Artificial intelligence and Databases.

In view of the above, ChatGPT, PPGIS, Machine Learning, Bibliometrics penetrating every sphere of social and professional life, there has been an increasing hype surrounding the application of these research support

tools/algorithms to more complex challenges in education, sciences, technology and healthcare, such as enabling diagnostics and facilitating drug discovery and medical research (Rice et al., 2024). These research support tools are not a single technology but a constellation of Machine Learning (ML), neural networks, and Natural Language Processing (NLP).. However, in the 21st century, there has been tremendous increase with the use of a several research support tools by Post Graduate Students, Researchers and the research community at large.

There is an ongoing debate on whether these research support tools is replacing the creativity of young researchers with machine-generated language, providing an easy way out, or is only being used to help guide research conducted by them. As expressed by Ale Ibrahim, student researchers face many problems and challenges including topic selection, lack of access to appropriate literature, lack of research knowledge and skills, poor reference management, and data collection and interpretation. While these research support tools can help mitigate a lot of these issues for students, there remain certain obstacles including privacy and security concerns, a lack of human engagement, and technological and data accuracy limits.

Statement of the Problems

In recent years, technological advancements have significantly transformed the way research is conducted, with a wide range of research support tools becoming integral to the research process. These research support tools includes, Data Analysis Tool, Reference Management Tools, Artificial Intelligence and Statistical Package for the Social Science among others .Sallam, (2023) states that substantial proportion of researchers now rely on these tools to enhance the quality and efficiency of their work.

Based on the preliminary investigation conducted by the researchers which revealed that a great number of postgraduate students remain unaware of these available tools and those that are aware do not utilize them effectively in their research endeavors, this could lead to under-utilization of available research tools in many libraries. Therefore, this study highlights the need for a comprehensive

exploration of the use of research support tools among Postgraduate Students at Modibbo Adama University, Yola.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study is to investigate the application and use of research support tools by postgraduate students of Faculty of Social and Management Science of Modibbo Adama University Yola, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Identify the types of research support tools mostly applied and used by postgraduate Students of Modibbo Adama University Yola, Nigeria.
2. Determine the level of application and use of research support tools by postgraduate Students of Modibbo Adama University Yola, Nigeria.
3. Ascertain the challenges associated with the application and use of research support tools by postgraduate Students of Modibbo Adama University Yola, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions formulated to guide the study:

1. What are the types of the research support tools mostly applied and used by postgraduate Students of Modibbo Adama University Yola, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of application and use of the research support tools by postgraduate Students of Modibbo Adama University Yola, Nigeria?
3. What are the challenges associated with the application and use of research support tools by Postgraduate students of Modibbo Adama University Yola, Nigeria?

Literature Review

Research support tools play a vital role in the educational attainment among postgraduate students. Sallam (2023) conducted a study on *the Use of Research Support Tools* among undergraduate students at the Nigerian Open University, Abuja study center. The research aimed to assess the level of awareness and usage of research support tools among these students. Academic research, grounded in principles of integrity and ethics, is essential for advancing knowledge

and maintaining scholarly trust. The study's findings revealed that while the students were generally aware of the available research support tools which aid in their academic pursuit. They further revealed that they frequently used and utilized these research support tools for optimum result orientation, while a minority of respondents expressed the need for wide awareness among the students and additional training to enhance productivity.

Reference management tools such as Zotero, EndNote, and Mendeley are widely adopted by students to organize sources, generate citations, and create bibliographies. According to Thanuskodi (2019), students using these tools show improved citation accuracy and reduced instances of plagiarism. These tools not only save time but also help in maintaining consistency in referencing styles. Data analysis tools like SPSS, R, NVivo, and Excel play a vital role in the analytical phase of student research. A study by Ahmad et al. (2021) found that postgraduate students who were trained in data analysis software demonstrated higher levels of confidence and accuracy in interpreting research data. These tools support both quantitative and qualitative analysis, making them versatile across disciplines.

The increasing complexity of academic research has led to the development and widespread adoption of various research support tools. These tools range from data analysis software and citation managers to artificial intelligence (AI)-based writing assistants. Postgraduate students, in particular, benefit significantly from these tools as they navigate the demanding process of conducting and presenting original research. The integration of these tools into the research process not only improves efficiency but also enhances the quality of academic output. Christou, (2023), he strategically outlined some of these research support tools not limited to the following: Data Analysis Tool, Writing Support Tools, Reference Management Software, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning Tools, ChatGPT and Grammarly- Online Grammar & Spelling Checker

Research support tools are software or digital platforms designed to assist researchers in various stages of the research process, such as data collection, analysis, referencing, and writing. According to Smith E. and Gupta A. (2021), the accessibility and effectiveness of such tools are pivotal in supporting postgraduate

students, especially those navigating complex academic requirements. The tools not only enhance efficiency but also promote adherence to ethical research standards, ensuring credibility and scholarly trust. In a study conducted by Ale Ebrahim (2023) to examine the level of research support tool usage among selected staff members of the University of Ibadan, findings revealed that the majority of respondents judiciously utilized these tools for their research and academic activities. This frequent usage resulted in a high level of satisfaction with the tools and significantly contributed to the timely completion of tasks, ultimately enhancing productivity and fostering a results-oriented approach. Postgraduate students often rely heavily on research support tools to manage the increased complexity of their academic responsibilities. Studies by Ahmed and Johnson (2020) indicate that these students use reference management tools like Zotero, EndNote, and Mendeley, along with platforms like Grammarly for editing and SPSS for statistical analysis. High satisfaction levels are linked to the perceived user-friendliness, reliability, and relevance of these tools to specific research needs.

Research Support Tools have become essential for postgraduate students to manage their research effectively. However, the level of use and satisfaction with these tools varies among students. This literature examines the existing research on the level of satisfaction with the use of research support tools as reported by Ale Ibrahim, (2023). These research support tools has led to improved organization and time management. It also enhanced collaboration and communication for increased productivity and efficiency. These research support tools have tremendously helped them in better data management and analysis.

Despite numerous benefits associated with the use of Research Support Tools by Postgraduate Students, they tend to encounter several challenges in the quest of using these research support tools. (Thompson, 2020) highlighted some of these challenges to include the following:

1. **i Limited Access to Research Tools:** One of the most significant challenges faced by postgraduate students is the limited access to certain research support tools. Many advanced software programs, such as **SPSS, MATLAB,** and **Stata**, require expensive licenses, which may not be available to students outside of well-funded institutions.
2. **ii Lack of Training and Technical Expertise:** Even when research tools are available, postgraduate students often face a steep learning curve due to a lack of adequate training. Many students report that they are not provided with formal instruction on how to use research tools like data analysis software, citation managers, or AI-based writing assistants
3. **iii Cognitive Overload and Tool Overuse:** Postgraduate students frequently experience cognitive overload due to the wide array of research support tools available to them. With so many tools designed to help with various aspects of the research process, students may feel overwhelmed by the need to learn and integrate multiple tools into their workflow.
4. **iv Technical Limitations and Compatibility Issues:** These are another common challenge encountered by postgraduate students when using research support tools. Software updates, system requirements, and compatibility across devices and platforms can hinder the smooth use.
5. **Ethical Concerns and Over-Reliance on AI Tools:** The integration of AI-based tools in research presents ethical challenges, particularly concerning the originality of work and the authenticity of the research process, raising concerns about academic integrity (Huang & Tan, 2023).

Methodology

The researchers adopted quantitative research design. Questionnaire was designed as instrument for data collection. Having 215 postgraduate students as the total population, the Researcher sampled all the Postgraduate Students across the Faculty using Consensus sampling technique because the number is manageable as the subject for this study. Results collected were analyzed using frequency and simple percentage for research question 1 and 3 with 50% as benchmark for acceptability or rejection while research question 2 was analyzed

using mean with 2.5 as the mean value used as benchmark for acceptability or rejection for the findings respectively. The presentation, analysis and interpretation of data are done on tables.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the types of research support tools applied and used among postgraduate Students of Modibbo Adama University Yola, Nigeria?

Table 1: Types of Research Support Tools Applied and used By Postgraduate Students

S/N	Research Support Tool	YES		NO	
		F	%	F	%
1	Data Analysis Tools	84	64.6	46	35.4
2	Writing Support Tools	80	61.5	50	38.5
3	Reference Management Software	87	66.9	43	33.1
4	AI and Machine Learning Tools	92	70.8	38	29.2
5	Research Productivity & Time management	82	63.1	48	36.9
6	ChatG.P.T	85	65.4	45	34.6
7	Grammarly and Spelling Checker	90	69.2	40	30.8

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 1 indicates that 84(64.6%) of the students used Data Analysis Tool with 46(35.4%) shows that they do not, 80(61.5%) of the students used Writing Support Tools while 50(38.5%) do not, 87(66.9%) revealed that they used Reference Management Software while 43(33.1%) shows that they do not, 92(70.8%) of the respondents revealed that they used AI and Machine Learning Tools while 38(29.2%) shows that they do not, 82(63.1%) of the students used Research Productivity & Time management while 48(36.9%) shows that they do not, 85(65.4%) of the respondents revealed that they use ChatG.P.T while 45(34.6%)

shows that the do not use about ChatG.P.T, 90(69.2%) indicates that the respondents used Grammarly and Spelling Checker while 40(30.8%) of them shows that they do not. This shows clearly that the students used AI and Machine Learning Tools most having the highest response with 92(70.8%). Hence, we can conclude that the respondents applied and used all the research support tools.

Research Question 2: What is the level of application and use of research support tools among postgraduate students of Modibbo Adama University Yola, Nigeria?

Table 2: Level of Application and use of Research Support Tools by Postgraduate Students

S N	Research Support Tools	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	Mea n	Decisio n
1	Data Analysis Tools	5 5	42. 3	3 5	27	2 5	19. 2	1 5	11. 5	3.00	Used
2	Writing Support Tools	6 5	50	4 0	30. 8	1 5	11. 5	1 0	7.7	3.23	Used
3	Reference Mgt. Software	5 0	38. 5	5 0	38. 5	1 5	11. 5	1 5	11. 5	3.04	Used
4	AI Machine Learning Tools	7 0	53. 8	4 0	30. 8	1 5	11. 5	5	3.9	3.35	Used
5	Research Productivity	6 0	46. 2	4 5	34. 6	1 5	11. 5	1 0	7.7	3.19	Used

	& Time managemen t										
6	ChatG.P.T	5 2	40	4 0	30. 8	2 8	21. 5	1 0	7.7	3.03	Used
7	Grammarly & Spelling Checker	5 0	38. 5	4 0	30. 8	2 5	19. 2	1 5	11. 5	2.96	Used
										3.1	Used
Grand Mean											

Source: Field Survey, 2025

From the above table 2, the respondents revealed that their level of application and use for Writing Support Tools stands at 3.00 mean value, while Writing Support Tools 3.23 and Reference Management Software at 3.04 with AI and Machine Learning Tools having 3.35, Research Productivity & Time Management has 3.19 while Chatgpt shows 3.03 while Grammarly and Spelling Checker has 2.96. This shows that AI and Machine Learning Tools has the highest respondents while showing that all the Research Support Tools being applied and used generally with 3.1 as grand mean.

Research Question 3: What are the challenges faced with the application and use of research support tools by postgraduate Students of Modibbo Adama University Yola, Nigeria.

Table 3: Challenges Faced with the Application and use of Research Support Tools.

S/N	Challenges faced with Research Support Tools	YES		NO	
		F	%	F	%
1	Lack of awareness of research support tools	62	47.7	68	52.3
2	Unfamiliarity with research support tools	74	56.9	56	43.1
3	Lack of network connectivity	86	66.2	44	33.8
4	Problem while accessing e-resource remotely	78	60	52	40
5	Training requirement	92	70.8	38	29.2
6	Subscription bundle	85	65.4	45	34.6

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The table above indicate that 62(47.75%) are unaware of the research support tools while 68(52.3%) shows that they are aware of these research support tools, 74(56.9%) shows that they are faced with Unfamiliarity with research support tools while 56(43.1%) said otherwise, 86(66.2%) revealed that they are posed with the challenge of Lack of network connectivity while 44(33.8%) said it doesn't affect them, 78(60%) are also faced with Problem while accessing e-resource remotely and 52(40%) said otherwise. 92(70.8%) of these students indicates that they faced the issue of Training requirement as their major challenge while 38(29.2%) said that has not been an issue with them while 85(65.4%) revealed that they are confronted with the challenge of subscription bundle with 45(34.6%) stating that as not an issue to them. To this end, one can categorically state that, the Postgraduate students are faced with Training requirements as their major challenge to the application and use of these Research Support Tools with 92(70.8%). To this end, while challenges are notable by the respondents pointing training requirement, subscription bundle and Lack of network connectivity as the most pressing challenges.

Summary of findings

The summary of the findings were formulated based on the findings of the study:

1. The finding shows that all research support tools are widely applied and used across varying degrees with **AI and Machine Learning tools** having the most used research support tool.
2. The findings revealed that majority of respondents indicated that research tools were highly applicable and useful in carrying out research and academic purposes.
3. The findings reveal that the respondents recognize the challenges associated with applying and using research support pointing training requirement, subscription bundle and Lack of network connectivity as the most pressing challenges.

Conclusion:

The study concludes that if the research support tools are effectively used, utilizing their actual potential, then postgraduate students can attain their objectives in achieving their academic goals and career. Finally, the study recommends various research support tools available has helped the Postgraduate Students of Modibbo Adama University Yola in carrying out their research and academic pursuit while leveraging the modern advancements, some of the Postgraduate Students are aware but Faculty members and researchers needs to be trained more to get the actual benefits attached with the use of the available Research Support Tools.

Recommendations

From the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Institutions should organize regular training sessions and workshops to deepen postgraduate students' understanding and effective use of these research support tools.
2. It is important for management of the institutions to further integrate these research support tools into the academic curriculum, ensuring that they are

- systematically incorporated into research assignments, projects, and coursework.
3. The University management should improve Internet connectivity and prioritize the development of comprehensive, hands-on training programs that are specifically designed to help postgraduate students master the research support tools.

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